

Direct Gravimetric Determination of Copper(II) with a New Reagent, 3-(*o*-Carboxyphenyl)-1-*o*-tolyl-triazene-*N*-oxide

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3-(*o*-Carboxyphenyl)-1-*o*-tolyl-triazene-*N*-oxide has been used for the gravimetric determination of 2-30 mg Cu^{II}. The green complex, Cu(C₁₄O₈N₃H₁₁) is precipitated in the pH range 3-9 adjusted with aqueous caustic soda and hydrochloric acid, and is weighed as such after drying at 110-120°. Interferences caused by Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cr^{II}, Fe^{II}, Bi^{III}, Al^{III}, Pb^{II}, Sn^{II}, As^{III}, Sb^{III}, Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, V^V, Nb^V, Ta^V, Rh^{III} and Os^{IV} could be overcome by adjustment of pH and by using tartrate as the masking agent, while the effects of Fe^{III} and Be^{II}, Hg^{II} and U^{IV} are removed by ammonium bifluoride, potassium iodide, and ammonium acetate, respectively. Tartrate does not interfere while the effect of oxalate, citrate, F⁻, SCN⁻, PO₄³⁻, BO₃³⁻ and AsO₄³⁻ could be removed simply by the control of pH. The reagent has also been used in the determination of copper in alloys. The average relative error is ± 0.50% and relative standard deviation is ± 0.30.

A CRITICAL examination¹⁻⁵ of the important gravimetric methods for the determination of copper(II) with organic reagents indicates that the new reagent, 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-*o*-tolyl-triazene-*N*-oxide, recommended in this communication for the gravimetric determination of copper(II) is one of the sensitive reagents for the metal ions. The reagent is selective for Cu^{II} at a suitable pH and/or in presence of masking agent. It reacts with Cu^{II} quantitatively at the pH range 3-9, forming greenish, thermally stable complex, Cu(C₁₄O₈N₃H₁₁). The procedure described is a simple one and consumes less time. The reagent has been successfully applied for the determination of copper in presence of diverse ions and in its alloys.

Experimental

Preparation of reagent: *o*-Nitrotoluene was reduced with Zn dust and NH₄Cl in aqueous solution (containing little alcohol) to *o*-tolylhydroxylamine. It was then coupled with diazotised anthranilic acid below 5°. The pH was raised to 5 by adding sodium acetate when a very light yellow precipitate was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol to yield the reagent, m.p. 160° (Found: C, 62.18; H, 4.73; N, 15.68. Calcd. C, 61.98; H, 4.83; N, 15.49%).

Copper(II) solution: Electrolytically pure copper was dissolved in nitric acid and to this was added concentrated sulphuric acid (3-4 ml) and the solution evaporated until white fumes evolved. The metal content was determined in the usual way⁷. A Systronics pH meter was used to control the pH values.

General procedure: To an aliquot of standard solution of copper (2-30 mg Cu) was added a solution of sodium potassium tartrate (10 ml, 10%). Tartrate was not needed below pH 4.5. It was diluted to 150-200 ml and the pH adjusted to 3-9 with aqueous caustic soda and hydrochloric acid. The mixture was heated on water bath and a hot ethanolic solution of the reagent (0.05-0.25 gm) was added with constant stirring. The precipitate formed was digested on water bath for 20-30 min with occasional stirring. The greenish complex was then filtered hot through Gooch crucible (no. 3), washed several times with hot distilled water and dried at 110-120° to constant weight. The results of several determinations of Cu^{II} are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} WITH 3-(*o*-CARBOXY-PHENYL)-1-*o*-TOLYL-TRIAZENE-*N*-OXIDE

Cu taken mg	Weight of complex mg		Cu found mg		Relative error %	
	10.85	10.87	2.07	2.075	+0.53	+0.73
8.84	46.00	46.21	8.78	8.82	-0.72	-0.27
29.48	153.65	154.80	29.33	29.55	-0.51	+0.24

Procedure in presence of diverse ions: A known volume of Cu^{II} and foreign cation or anion, and 1.0-1.5 gm of suitable masking agent, where necessary, were diluted to 200 ml. The pH of the mixture was adjusted around 4.0, Cu^{II} was then determined as described under general procedure. Table 2 records the results.

Determination of Cu^{II} in alloys: Accurately weighed standard alloy (200 mg) was dissolved

in dil. nitric acid and evaporated slowly with conc. H₂SO₄ (3-4 ml) until the evolution of dense fumes of sulphur trioxide ceased. The content were cooled, filtered in a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark. The determination of Cu^{II} was then carried out with the prepared solution in the usual way. The results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Cu^{II} FROM DIVERSE IONS
Cu taken : 8.84 mg

Diverse ions added mg	Masking agent	Weight of complex mg	Cu found mg	Relative error %
Oxalate (100)	—	46.0	8.78	- 0.68
Citrate (100)	—	46.50	8.88	+ 0.45
Tartrate (1,500)	—	46.48	8.87	+ 0.34
Fluoride (500)	—	46.21	8.82	- 0.23
Thiocyanate (200)	—	46.38	8.85	+ 0.11
Phosphate (100)	—	46.44	8.86	+ 0.23
Borate (100)	—	46.28	8.83	- 0.11
Arsenate (100)	—	46.15	8.81	- 0.34
Zn ⁺⁺ (50)	Na-K-tartrate	46.48	8.87	+ 0.34
Cd ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.50	8.88	+ 0.45
Mg ⁺⁺ (200)	"	46.10	8.80	- 0.45
Al ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.44	8.86	+ 0.23
Bi ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.46	8.87	+ 0.34
As ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.36	8.85	+ 0.11
Sb ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.52	8.88	+ 0.45
MoO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	"	46.21	8.82	- 0.23
WO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	"	46.54	8.88	+ 0.45
Pb ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.36	8.85	+ 0.11
Mn ⁺⁺ (30)	"	46.48	8.87	+ 0.34
Ni ⁺⁺ (30)	"	46.28	8.83	- 0.11
Co ⁺⁺ (30)	"	46.48	8.87	+ 0.34
Ta ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.38	8.85	+ 0.11
Nb ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.21	8.82	- 0.23
Rh ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.44	8.86	+ 0.23
Os ⁺⁺ (50)	"	46.48	8.87	+ 0.34
UO ₂ ⁺⁺ (50)	Ammonium acetate	46.36	8.85	± 0.11
Fe ⁺⁺ (50)	NH ₄ HF ₂	46.44	8.86	+ 0.23
Be ⁺⁺ (200)	"	46.28	8.83	- 0.11
Hg ⁺⁺ (50)	KI	46.21	8.82	- 0.23

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} IN ALLOYS

Samples	Copper certified	Copper found
Tin bronze	77.69%	77.88%
Aluminium bronze	85.90%	85.83%
Brass	67.40%	67.31%
Manganese bronze	57.20%	57.29%

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH and reagent concentration : A set of experiments was carried out under stated conditions but with variation of pH. It was observed

that the precipitation of copper complex commenced at pH 2 and was quantitative between pH 3.0 and 9.0. In another series of experiments the pH was fixed around 6.0 and the amount of the reagent was varied. It was found that 1.5 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent was sufficient for complete precipitation and excess reagent (upto 5 fold excess) showed no adverse effect on the determination. The precipitation was not quantitative below pH 3.0 and above pH 9.0.

Properties, composition of the complex : The copper complex with 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-*o*-tolyl-triazene-*N*-oxide melts at 262°(d). The complex is sparingly soluble in water and in 20% ethanol but soluble in absolute ethanol. The complex was analysed for copper by iodometric method and nitrogen by Dumas method. (Found : Cu, 19.07; N, 13.0. Cu(C₁₄O₈N₃H₁₁) calcd. Cu, 19.09; N, 12.62%). The ir band at 3235 cm⁻¹ (N-H stretch), and 1665 and 1264 cm⁻¹ (-COOH and N-O stretches) in free ligand disappear and shift to lower frequencies, respectively in the complex. This indicates that chelation takes place through N-H and COOH by proton displacement and through O of N-O with the formation of M-O bond. The absence of band for water in the complex spectra suggests that it has apparently a tri-coordinated structure and is probably dimeric one where N-oxide oxygen or the carboxyl oxygen acting as the bridging atom.

Interferences : The determination of Cu^{II} was not possible in the presence of disodium EDTA and cyanide while large excess of citrate, oxalate, thiocyanate and phosphate masked Cu^{II} partially.

Precision and accuracy : The average relative error in the determination of Cu^{II} by the procedure described is ±0.50% and the relative standard deviation ±0.30.

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